

EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES FOR TEACHING ESP COURSE

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Abstract: In this article we aim to learn and clarify some handful methods and techniques for teaching ESP classes. It also sets out important aspects of four skills: reading, listening, writing, speaking. Using various techniques and encouraging ESP learners to become independent, to seek out learning opportunities on their own and increase ESP students' learning motivation. The concern of ESP to design appropriate courses for various groups of learners according to their needs and general English concerns on vocabulary work, spelling, grammar, pronunciation, language functions.

Keywords: English, Teaching, Techniques, Specific groups, Lecturer, Environment.

INTRODUCTION

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) started to emerge as a field in the late 1960, following the Second World War, a time when more and more people desired to learn English to conduct businesses in international technology and commerce. These eventually required English courses to be designed for specific groups of learners, taking into account the linguistic characteristics of learners' area of work and study [6.90]. As a result of these developments, and growing research in educational psychology, tailoring ESP courses according to learner needs historically played a pivotal role in both the design and teaching of ESP [8.56].

Today, English Language Teaching (ELT) professionals make a distinction between English for General Purposes (EGP) and ESP. While EGP aims at providing

students with a solid foundation of English language so that they will build on it in future, ESP refers to the teaching of English for such specific purposes as academic, and occupational [2.201]. ESP is therefore mainly concerned with teaching the specialist language, and “involves teaching and learning the specific skills and language needed by particular learners for a particular purpose” [4.5]. The words “particular” and “purpose” in Day and Krzanowski’s definition deserve further attention. “Particularness” is of great importance in ESP as disciplinary study is the main focus of it, and “purpose” why learners learn ESP is specifically related to their needs in the workplace, with special emphasis on chunks and patterns of language used in particular disciplines and professions. In short, ESP aims “to develop the competencies needed to function in a discipline, profession, or workplace” [2.6].

As a consequence of its learner-centered nature, teaching ESP imposes a lot of demands on teachers. The first of these demands is related with the knowledge base an ESP teacher should possess. What is more, although content knowledge is a must for teachers, it is not enough on its own. Teachers should also be able to present content knowledge in meaningful ways to learners, requiring additional knowledge called pedagogical content knowledge [6.45].

Another demand is related with the roles of ESP teachers. An ESP teacher takes on different roles and responsibilities. In addition to acting as teachers, they also play a key role as curriculum developers [9.21], as well as course designers, materials writers, collaborators, evaluators, and researchers [5.35]. It would not be wrong to assert that ESP teachers need to carry out additional tasks that teachers who teach EGP do not usually carry out. ESP teachers are specialists, “often needs analysts, then designers and implementers of specialised curricula”. However, the literature has not fully considered the implications of these roles.

METHODOLOGY

To meet the students' need, the methodology of ESP should be based on the fundamental principle of core language needs of target learners and be facilitated

with adopt teaching material and practice [1.144.]ESP teaching learning purposes is communicative competence, so that learner-centered and more communicative activities should the emphasis in ESP approach. ESP teaching learning process in the classroom is learner-centered, in the way that the learner's reasons for learning to use a specific area of the English language in the shortest term possible become the basis of the teaching. Curriculum and Syllabus Design. Curriculum means a set or system plan and arrangement about the content and the learning material which will be a compass in teaching learning process. Curriculum is a theoretical document that is guided by study programs in educational systems or institutions. Hence, curriculum is a program which must be referred to by teachers and students in teaching and learning process to achieve national education goals. Designing a syllabus to a specific group in a particular situation is not simple task, it is about designing the goals of learning a language based on the needs of learners and the target. The syllabus tends to represent, reflects the idea of the originator of language learning. the syllabus is a representative of current knowledge and a certain ability that made by designer's view of language and how it is to learn, how the language can be taught or properly presented to learners, and how it can be produced productively during learning [2.83] Developing ESP Materials. ESP Practitioners have to choose the suitable materials based on the need analysis and syllabus design, accordingly to the content of the course. The appropriate materials are providing a stimulus of learning and could be a good motivation factor. Teaching materials are small parts that are cut and rearranged to suit the needs, abilities and interests of students in the lesson [3.27]. The most common ESP teachers use existing textbooks as their handbook in teaching rather than uses self-generated materials because the ESP teachers are not the expert of specialist subject. Teachers have to develop the materials from an authentic material because suitable materials to ESP course are not easy to find. Assessment. Assessment is the processes to getting know how far the students acquire the course given by the teacher. Assessment is a tool to measure

the students' quality in learning. It is the way to know the students' achievement at the end of study. Test is shown certain formal types that usually organized carefully. The assessment is not used only to determine the students' ability in acquiring skills and knowledge but also to evaluate the effectiveness of the teaching. They are it measures progress, achievement/outcomes in terms of knowledge and skills; provides the basis for decisions on whether a student is ready to proceed, enables students to obtain feedback on their learning helps students to improve their performance and enables staff to evaluate the effectiveness of there.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the classroom, the lecturer used the direct teaching strategy in order to teach the students. They practiced this kind of teaching strategy to present the material in a depth conception and explanation to the students. This direct teaching strategy is mostly directed by the lecturer who creates the class environment that is oriented on the students' academic competence. Direct teaching refers to academically focus, lecturer-directed classroom using sequenced and structured material. The focus of direct teaching strategy is academic and lecturer centered, using a structured curriculum useful for teaching skills and acquiring new information [4.298]. Within this focus the lecturer convinces that the business of the classroom is learning. The lecturers managed the situation in teaching learning process very well. They can handle the students who got problems in learning English by using variety strategies in the teaching learning process. They do not only use the conventional method, but they modify many strategies in teaching. The lecturer used many strategies in every meeting and It made the students interesting in learning, so they did not feel bored in learning process. The various strategy creates attractive atmosphere in teaching learning process such as that using strategy is the lecturer's way to give the information and experiences and cognitive process to the students [5.65]. The lecturers use strategies to teach and to enrich the students' experience related to the material. The lecturers uses an appropriate strategy related to the material. Some

strategies in presenting the material are identified the purpose of teaching material, use graphic rules and patterns to aid and bottom-up decoding (for beginning level learners) and use efficient technique for relatively rapid comprehension (for intermediate to advance levels) [7.292]. The lecturers prepare and select the effective lessons to be used as the instruction materials purposefully, thoughtfully, and precise. Teaching strategies directly are focused on developing students' thinking based on instructional process. The strategies for teaching and learning are cannot be separated. The lecturers have to monitor the progress of each student, to take advantage of some moments to reinforce concepts or introduce new concepts, and to make decisions about appropriate needed. Thus, in the reading lesson it is strongly believed that our role in preparing lecturers involves educating individuals who can draw on their knowledge base and experiences to make informed critical decisions that positively influence the lives of children and adolescents.

CONCLUSION

ESP teachers need to learn as much as they can about their students' professional field to improve the course planning process (Day & Krzanowski, 2011). They do not seem to agree about what students really need and where they should get at by the end of the course. A needs analysis study involving the opinions of all stakeholders should be conducted before designing the curriculum.

When it comes to program implementation, teachers reported that they learned it through experience, so there should be more collaboration among ESP teachers since only through collegial support can short-term needs of teachers be met in an effective manner. ESP teachers feel insecure when working on their own in the teaching of ESP. They look for the support of other colleagues. Thus, we suggest collaboration be encouraged, and more coordination meetings be arranged in the department. Further, ESP teachers seem to become more confident in the teaching of ESP, material preparation and assessment after each year they teach the course.

Thus, the experienced and less experienced should always communicate ideas, and share experiences.

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